

**Secondary Prevention Efficacy Variability in MI Survivors: Introduction of the
Unmet Risk Index**

[Preprint]

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Abstract

Background: Secondary prevention following myocardial infarction (MI) often fails to consider individual risk profiles, potentially reducing intervention efficacy. This study aims to introduce the Unmet Risk Index (UMRI), which adjusts the risk of cardiovascular event recurrence relative to the baseline risk of a first event, for evaluating secondary prevention effectiveness. A higher UMRI indicates lower efficacy of secondary prevention.

Methods: A synthetic cohort of 26,880,000 MI survivor profiles was generated using the Atherosclerotic Cardiovascular Disease (ASCVD) and Second Manifestations of Arterial Disease (SMART) calculators. Profiles were categorized into paradoxical (<1, i.e., have a secondary risk that is lower than their baseline risk), low, intermediate, and high UMRI groups and compared for baseline characteristics of typical group prototypes. Multivariable logistic regression was used to identify predictors of a high UMRI.

Results: The analysis revealed distinct characteristics within the high UMRI group, including a higher proportion of females (75.8%), and a younger median age of 46 years. In contrast, the paradoxical UMRI group showed high rates of conventional risk factors such as diabetes (61.9%) and smoking (58.3%), and especially high systolic blood pressure (median 160 mmHg) despite the highest rates of antihypertensive treatment. Multivariable analysis identified female sex as the strongest predictor of high UMRI (OR 16.0256, $p < 0.001$), followed by non-smoking status (OR 11.6822, $p < 0.001$), and younger age.

Conclusion: The UMRI provides insight into secondary prevention for MI survivors, underscoring the need for personalized strategies to effectively address the wide variation in patient risk profiles.

Keywords: myocardial infarction, secondary prevention, Unmet Risk Index, risk factors, personalized medicine

Introduction

The paradigm of secondary prevention following a myocardial infarction (MI) has traditionally embraced a universal approach, advocating broad-based interventions aimed at mitigating cardiovascular (CV) risk factors such as hypertension, diabetes, and smoking.¹⁻³ This strategy, however, often fails to account for the nuanced risk profiles of individual patients, particularly those whose MI occurred in the absence of these conventional risk markers⁴. The resultant one-size-fits-all approach may thus leave a subset of patients with minimal benefit from interventions that do not align with their unique risk profile.

The comprehension of current secondary prevention's true efficacy in lower-risk MI patients is further complicated by the observation that the rate of recurrent CV events under secondary prevention is lower in low-risk MI patients.⁵ This phenomenon may lead to an assumption that the secondary prevention is effective in this population, while the low rate of recurrency may be attributed to the inherent lower risk, rather than to efficacy of the preventive measures. Supporting this possibility are the findings of Hammer et al., who showed that over a decade of treating ACS patients with guideline directed medical therapy (GDMT), a decline in recurrent events was seen only for high-risk patients and not for intermediate and low-risk patients, despite the latter groups having absolute lower rates of recurrency.⁶ This discrepancy underscores a critical gap in our current preventive strategies, suggesting that they may not be sufficiently tailored to meet the diverse needs of the MI survivor population.

To aid in the clarification of the efficacy of secondary prevention for different risk profile MI survivors, we propose the Unmet Risk Index (UMRI) which adjusts the risk for a recurrent event to the baseline risk (which reflects the risk profile): $\text{Unmet risk index} = \text{Risk for recurrence of a CV event} / \text{Baseline risk for a CV event}$. The UMRI articulates the gap between the perceived baseline risk and the observed risk after a first CV event. This gap widens as the unknown, thus unmet, portion of the risk increases. An unclear etiology for the first CV event is in concert with a mistakenly low baseline risk perception, and again with inefficient secondary prevention treatment that leads to higher than acceptable secondary risk. Coupling these effects widens the gap and increases the UMRI.

In this study, we aimed to introduce the UMRI and its potential usage, by exploring it in a large and diverse assortment of MI survivor profiles.

Methods

Study population

The essential components of the UMRI are the baseline risk of a patient to undergo a first-ever MI, and the same patients' risk for undergoing another MI after their first one, under the current secondary prevention treatment. As both these risks can be estimated for a given MI patient profile through two medical risk calculators: the Atherosclerotic Cardiovascular Disease (ASCVD) risk estimator plus,⁶ which provides a baseline (primary prevention) 10-year risk for CV event, and the Second Manifestations of Arterial Disease (SMART) risk score,⁷ which provides a 10-year risk for recurrence of CV event – we elected to generate the study population

synthetically from the iteration of such calculators, and to use this cohort to demonstrate the UMRI and explore the typical patient profile in different UMRI groups. The decision to use these specific calculators was driven by the uniqueness of the SMART calculator as the only calculator that provides the risk for a recurrent event under secondary prevention, and thereafter by the similarity of the ASCVD calculator to SMART calculator both in risk estimation for 10 years, and in the fields of input.

The method used to generate this simulated cohort from medical calculators will be detailed in a separate publication. Briefly, by applying a cartesian product to the input factors of both the ASCVD and the SMART calculators, we created a dataset representing every combination of risk factors. Then, to align with our study design, we introduced specific constraints, such as resetting the 'time in years since first diagnosis of CV disease' to zero (to simulate a patient right after their first MI), and to achieve a tractable number of profiles, we adjusted the resolution of continuous variables, such as lowering the resolution of systolic blood pressure to 10 mmHg increments (instead of 1 mmHg increments). This method resulted in the assembly of an extensive synthetic cohort of 26,880,000 unique profiles, each reflecting a potential patient scenario for first myocardial infarction (MI) survivors, coupled with their baseline risk for a first MI and their risk for recurrence under secondary prevention after a first MI. This approach ensured the cohort's practicality for analysis and the comprehensive examination of the Unmet Risk Index (UMRI) across varied patient profiles.

It is important to note that while this cohort meticulously represents every potential MI survivor profile based on the calculators' inputs, it does not mirror the real-world distribution of MI survivors. However, this unique dataset allows for an in-depth analysis of the UMRI and aids in identifying typical patient profiles within different UMRI categories, providing valuable insights for secondary prevention strategies.

Grouping of the cohort

Initially, we intended to categorize the cohort into three groups based on the Unmet Risk Index (UMRI): the first quartile (low UMRI), the intermediate UMRI, and the fourth quartile (high UMRI). However, recognizing a distinct category with $UMRI < 1$, which represents a 'paradoxical' scenario where patients exhibit a lower risk of recurrence after their first myocardial infarction (MI) compared to their baseline risk, we opted to separately identify this group. Consequently, we divided the cohort into four distinct groups for more detailed characterization: (1) $UMRI < 1$, termed as the 'paradoxical' group; (2) UMRI ranging from 1 to 1.2342, identified as the low UMRI group; (3) UMRI between 1.2343 and 2.5088, defined as the intermediate UMRI group; and (4) UMRI exceeding 2.5089, classified as the high UMRI group.

Statistical analysis

Continuous variables were represented by medians and interquartile ranges (IQR) and analyzed using the Kruskal-Wallis test to identify differences among groups. In instances where significant differences were detected by the Kruskal-Wallis test, yet the medians and IQRs appeared identical across groups—a scenario

common in large cohorts where minor differences may not be evident in rounded figures—we additionally reported means and standard deviations for a more detailed analysis. For categorical variables, we employed the Chi-square test to assess differences. Post-hoc pairwise comparisons were conducted using Tukey's Honestly Significant Difference (HSD) test for categorical variables and Bonferroni's correction for continuous variables to control for multiple comparisons.

Logistic regression analysis was applied to determine the independence and predictive strength of baseline characteristics for a high UMRI, indicating limited effectiveness of secondary prevention. This model included all evaluated factors. A p-value of less than 0.001 was set as the threshold for statistical significance, ensuring a stringent criterion for identifying meaningful differences.

Statistical analysis was carried out using R: A Language and Environment for Statistical Computing, R Core Team, R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria, 2020, <https://www.R-project.org>.

Results

Baseline characteristics of the cohort by the UMRI groups are presented in Table 1 and Figure 1. The distribution of female sex increased with UMRI levels, from 44.3% in the Paradoxical UMRI group to 75.8% in the High UMRI group. Median age demonstrated a decreasing trend with higher UMRI, with the median ages being 63 [Interquartile Range (IQR): 54-71], 62 [IQR: 52-71], 57 [IQR: 48-68], and 46 [IQR: 43-52] years, respectively. African race prevalence decreased with increasing UMRI, from 56.4% in the Paradoxical UMRI group to 34.9% in the High UMRI group.

The prevalence of the classical risk factors diabetes and smoking decreased with increasing UMRI, from 61.9% and 58.3% in the Paradoxical UMRI group to 32.0% and 27.1% in the High UMRI group, respectively. Concordantly, levels of systolic blood pressure and of total cholesterol levels decreased with increasing UMRI. High-sensitivity C-Reactive Protein (hsCRP) levels increased with UMRI, from a median of 1 [IQR: 0.2-8] in the Paradoxical UMRI group to 8 [IQR: 1-13] in the High UMRI group, with mean hsCRP also showing an upward trend.

Focusing on the 'paradoxical' UMRI group with a UMRI<1, they were found to have comparable age and female sex rates with the low UMRI group, but had higher rates of African race (56.4% vs. 47.8% in the low UMRI group), smoking and diabetes, and noticeably had higher levels of systolic blood pressure (median 160 [140-180] vs. 140 [110-160] in the low UMRI group), despite having higher rates of being treated with antihypertensive treatment (58.3% vs. 44.6% in the low UMRI group).

The logistic regression analysis results are detailed in Table 2. Female sex was found to be the strongest predictor of a high UMRI (OR 16.0256 [15.949-16.1031]), followed by not smoking (OR 11.6822 [11.6414-11.7371]), younger age, the absence of diabetes, and being of a non-African race (OR 5.01 [4.99-5.005]). In contrast, lower total cholesterol levels, and higher levels of hsCRP were found to be weaker predictors (OR 1.1501 [1.1497-1.1505] for every increase in 1.0 mg/dL of hsCRP) of a high UMRI.

Discussion

In this study, we introduced a new way to stratify MI Survivors, instead of addressing them as a homogenous group. By the utilization of the UMRI to assess the efficacy of secondary prevention, we can identify three prototypes of MI survivors.

One prototype includes those with a non-high but also non-paradoxical UMRI, encompassing patients from the low and intermediate UMRI groups, who reflect the 'regular' MI survivor, who have risk factors that are largely well-addressed by the current secondary prevention scheme. We expect the majority of patients in the real world to fall under this prototype.

A second interesting prototype includes those in the paradoxical UMRI group. As depicted by the contrast between the higher levels of systolic blood pressure despite higher rates of antihypertensive treatment, these patients are characterized by not-well-controlled risk factors. In these patients, the occurrence of their first MI serves as a 'wake-up call', after which the impact of the improved control of these risk factors that comes with the secondary prevention greatly outweighs the added risk that is associated with now have a history of MI. As such, the focus of intervention in this group needs to be not on their secondary prevention, which is efficacious, but on their primary prevention, i.e. on identifying them before the first MI and improve their control of risk factors, probably through educational efforts to lower smoking rates and improve adherence to medications and better primary physician follow up.

The third prototype is the original group of interest of this study, the high UMRI group. These are younger, non-African, mostly female patients, without classic

risk factors for MI. These include obvious non-classic-atherosclerosis-based MI cases, namely spontaneous coronary artery dissection (SCAD) patients who are typically young female patients, but also not-so-obvious cases whose characteristics difference from intermediate- and even low-UMRI is not that clear, as evident by the overlapping confidence intervals and non-neglectable frequency of classic risk factors such as diabetes (32%) and smoking (27.1%). This strengthens the need for the UMRI, as such patients can be falsely perceived as benefiting from the traditional secondary prevention due to their classic risk factors, when in fact if we take into consideration the rest of their characteristics, they end up not benefiting enough from it. Consequently, it raises the idea that if efforts to improve the secondary prevention in patients without risk factors, i.e. by finding non-classic to risk factors to target in this population, it will also benefit patients with classic risk factors. A follow-up clinical study is planned by our group with this argument in view.

Our multivariable analysis highlighted one factor above all that predicts poor benefit from secondary prevention—being of female sex. Multiple studies have demonstrated the different course of cardiovascular disease in females, starting with atypical symptoms,⁸ through lower performance of diagnostic tests for them,⁹ to worse cardiovascular outcomes.¹⁰ Our study aligns with these previous findings, accumulating a significant portion of the unknown and therefore unmet risk for females. This emphasizes the critical need for a tailored approach in secondary prevention strategies that address the unique physiological and clinical presentation of cardiovascular disease in women. Moreover, this insight underscores the importance of developing and implementing more personalized, gender-aware clinical guidelines that can better identify and manage the elevated risk in female

patients. The incorporation of gender-specific considerations into secondary prevention could not only improve outcomes for women but also enhance our understanding of cardiovascular disease mechanisms and treatment responses across the entire spectrum of patients.

To the best of our knowledge, the SMART calculator stands out as the sole model that predicts the risk of a recurrent cardiovascular event, particularly under the conditions of secondary prevention. Moreover, to our knowledge, no existing tool evaluates the efficacy of secondary prevention—a critical aspect not captured by the absolute risk predictions provided by the SMART calculator. The UMRI which addresses this gap, highlights the significant diversity within a group of myocardial infarction (MI) survivors who are currently perceived and managed as a homogeneous cohort. Within this framework, the development of the Unmet Risk Index (UMRI) is in line with the overarching goals of personalized medicine,^{11,12} especially in cardiovascular care^{13,14}. The UMRI also emphasizes the importance of continued research into discovering novel risk factors and therapeutic targets, aiming to enhance the personalization of care.

Limitations

This study has two main limitations. First, as mentioned before, its nature, being generated iteratively from medical calculators, leads to an unnatural and irrelevant distribution of patients, meaning that the frequency of the identified prototypes in real-life cannot be deducted from their frequency in the study. However, as the aim of this study was to introduce the UMRI and to describe the typical profiles of different UMRI groups – it was not limited by the lack of data of

the realistic frequency of them. Nevertheless, we are planning to complement the findings of this study with real-world data of MI survivors, to overcome this limitation, as well as to look for the non-classical risk factors discussed above. Second, it may suffer from limitations of the origins of the UMRI, i.e. the specific calculators it was derived from. Any inaccuracy in them would affect the absolute measured risks, that in reality may be higher or lower for both the primary and secondary estimation, especially in populations different than those in the original studies. In this context, it should also be noted that the two calculators we used were developed from data from different populations. The ASCVD used data from an American population, and the SMART used data from a European population – thus their pairing probably suffers from inherent inaccuracies. However, even if the risk estimates used for the calculations in our study are inaccurate, the concept of the index presented here stays valid.

Conclusion

Important diversity exists amongst MI survivors that can be demonstrated by usage of the UMRI. Attention should be turned patients with high UMRI, who do not benefit properly from current secondary prevention.

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Tables and figures

Table 1. Baseline Characteristics of MI Survivors Across Different UMRI Categories.

	Paradoxical (<1) UMRI N=14,363,053	Low UMRI N=3,128,801	Intermediate UMRI N=6,259,014	High UMRI N=3,129,132
Female sex - n (%)	6,364,890 (44.3)	1,373,868 (43.9)	3,330,779 (53.2)	2,370,463 (75.8)
Age, years - median [IQR]	63 [54-71]	62 [52-71]	57 [48-68]	46 [43-52]
African race - n (%)	8,094,104 (56.4)	1,494,094 (47.8)	2,758,870 (44.1)	1,092,932 (34.9)
Systolic blood pressure, mmHg - median [IQR]	160 [140-180]	140 [110-160]	120 [100-150]	110 [100-140]
Total cholesterol - median [IQR]	6 [5-7]	6 [5-7]	6 [5-7]	6 [4-7]
Total cholesterol - mean (SD)	6.0446 (1.4048)	6.064 (1.412)	6.011 (1.419)	5.708 (1.415)
HDL - median [IQR]	1.5 [1-2]	1.5 [1-2]	1.5 [1-2]	2 [1.5-2.5]
HDL – mean (SD)	1.5319 (0.6938)	1.4170 (0.6572)	1.4380 (0.6562)	1.7455 (0.6219)
Diabetes - n (%)	8,892,363 (61.9)	1,349,306 (43.1)	2,197,699 (35.1)	1,000,632 (32.0)

Smoking - n (%)	8,368,681 (58.3)	1,565,350 (50.0)	2,657,629 (42.5)	848,340 (27.1)
Taking antihypertensive medication - n (%)	8,368,150 (58.3)	1,394,957 (44.6)	2,493,905 (39.8)	1,182,988 (37.8)
eGFR - median [IQR]	90 [70-110]	90 [70-110]	90 [70-110]	90 [70-110]
eGFR - mean (SD)	89.2543 (19.0512)	90.427 (20.589)	90.895 (21.055)	91.206 (21.302)
hsCRP - median [IQR]	1 [0.2-8]	6 [1-11]	8 [1-13]	8 [1-13]
hsCRP - mean (SD)	4.6494 (5.1618)	6.673 (5.360)	7.174 (5.330)	7.374 (5.323)
ASCVD risk score, % within 10 years - median [IQR]	30.76 [19.61-46.4]	16.0 [10.6-25.0]	8.7 [5.6-14.1]	2.1 [1.1-3.4]
SMART risk score, % within 10 years - median [IQR]	18.15 [12.32-26.52]	17.7 [11.8-27.5]	14.3 [9.8-21.9]	8.6 [6.4-11.6]

UMRI: Unmet Risk Index. N: Number of participants in each category. IQR:

Interquartile Range. SD: Standard Deviation. HDL: High-Density Lipoprotein

eGFR: estimated Glomerular Filtration Rate. hsCRP: High-sensitivity C-Reactive

Protein. ASCVD: Atherosclerotic Cardiovascular Disease. SMART: Second

Manifestations of Arterial Disease

Table 2. Multivariable logistic regression of predictors of high UMRI. Ordered by strength of prediction

	Odds ratio [95% confidence interval]	p-value
Female sex	16.0256 [15.949-16.1031]	<0.001
No smoking	11.6822 [11.6414-11.7371]	<0.001
Younger age - for each 10-year reduction	10.0541 [10.016-10.079]	<0.001
No diabetes	6.8871 [6.8587-6.9156]	<0.001
Non-African race	5.01 [4.99-5.005]	<0.001
Not on antihypertensive medications	3.6778 [3.6643-3.6928]	<0.001
Higher HDL - for each 1.0 mmol/L increase	3.4436 [3.4336-3.4536]	<0.001
Lower systolic blood pressure - for each 20mmHg reduction	2.879 [2.873-2.8852]	<0.001
Lower total cholesterol - for each 1.0 mmol/L reduction	1.4754 [1.4734-1.4775]	<0.001
hsCRP - for each 1.0 mg/L increase	1.1501 [1.1497-1.1505]	<0.001
eGFR - for each 10.0 mL/min/1.73m ² increase	1.084 [1.083-1.0851]	<0.001

OR: Odds Ratio. CI: Confidence Interval

Figure 1. Demographic and Clinical Characteristics Across UMRI Categories.

Figure 1 Legend: Overview of participant characteristics and health metrics across UMRI categories. The figure combines categorical variables (upper row) and continuous health metrics (rows two to four), showcasing: Categorical data on race, sex, diabetes, smoking, and HTN medication use as bars. Continuous variables (Age, Systolic BP, Total Cholesterol, HDL, eGFR, hsCRP) as line charts with error bars representing median/IQR or mean/SD. Charts demonstrate variations across UMRI categories, providing insights into demographic and health-related disparities.